

A FAST MARCHING-LEVEL SETS APPROACH FOR THE DISTANCE FIELD COMPUTATION AND ITS APPLICATION IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING PROCESS PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

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ABSTRACT

The success of filling and curing stages in a liquid composite molding (LCM) depends on many variables such as locations of gates and vents, temperature distribution, flow rate, injection pressure, etc. A great challenge to obtain high quality finished parts is to accurately predict flow pattern using simulation for process design optimization. With the predicted process performance measures, the LCM process can be optimized through locating the gates and vents properly to prevent dry areas. It imposes that the flow has to be vent-oriented avoiding flow encounters and a desired resin flow pattern that achieves the vent uniformly. LCM simulation is computationally expensive because it needs an accurate solution of flow equations during the mold filling process. When simulating large computing times are not compatible with standard optimization techniques (for example for locating optimally the injection nozzles) or with process control that in general requires fast decision-makings. Since the flow fronts can be related to the distance of the flow path, in this work, we propose a numerical technique that computes numerically approximate distance fields by invoking computational geometry concepts that can be used for real time applications. Moreover, we present a computational and technological framework for developing tools based on artificial vision techniques. The computation is based on level sets and allows one to monitor the flow motion under dynamic behaviour during filling and establishes geometric reference benchmarks for robust processing. The main objective regarding to outline the capabilities of using geometric indicators for the advancing front pattern optimization and control has been accomplished and different experiments are shown.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) is a group of manufacturing processes widely used in the industry. The techniques in LCM most commonly referred in the literature are RTM (Resin Transfer Molding), LRI (Liquid Resin Infusion), RI (Resin Infusion) or VI (Vacuum Infusion), VARTM (Vacuum Resin Transfer Molding). These processes are commonly used in different manufacturing industry sectors such as: aeronautics, automobile, watersports, civil engineering, marine boat and Aeolian energy.

Presently, the use of artificial vision is growing in LCM processes with the top half-mold semi-rigid or transparent like VARTM (Vacuum Assisted RTM) or RI (Vacuum Infusion). This work experiments are focused in the Resin Infusion process where one tool face is made of transparent flexible film. Resin infusion process can be operated in low cost open molds with vacuum bags due to its low-pressure conditions. Our previous works [5] have been intended to achieve an artificial vision system to link the virtual (computational) and the real (technological) frameworks. Therefore, AV should be associated to techniques and algorithms with optimum computation that allow using the sensing information.

Resin Infusion (RI) process is one of the common techniques used in the industry for large composite parts production. This technique uses negative pressure to drive the resin into a textile preform. Fabric is laid dry into the mold and the vacuum is applied before the resin enters the cavity. Once a complete vacuum is achieved, resin is sucked into the mold via placed tubing. Figure 1 shows a diagram of this process.

Figure 1. Liquid Resin Infusion Process stages.

A suitable modeling of flow front's shapes advancement constrained by RI process during filling can be based on the continuous deformation of the vent oriented flow pattern due to the driving pressure from the inlet. One of the main objectives is that the flow achieves the contour vent uniformly to avoid pressure drop and guaranteeing complete filling. In RI, the flow front shape development is mainly conditioned by the arrangement of the channels allocation and the material variables that can evolve along the mold path.

The main awareness of this research [1],[2],[3] is to develop computational tools that should be based on the geometry of the flow path through the mold filling. A suitable modeling of flow front's shapes constrained by LCM processes can be based on next main assumptions:

- The flow fronts filling time can be related to the distance of the flow path from the inlet to the outlet.
- The deformation needed to prevent dry areas imposes that the flow has to be vent-oriented and avoiding flow encounters.

In terms of design and control strategies and in order to undertaking the complete mold filling achievement, the flow front can be monitored with suitable computational reference benchmarks proposed in this work. We propose a numerical technique that computes approximate distance fields by invoking computational geometry concepts. Moreover, we present a computational and

technological framework for developing tools based on artificial vision techniques

2 A LEVEL SET APPROACH IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING GEOMETRIC MODELLING

In this work a level set approach described in [1] is employed to compute the vent distance field of a given composite part. An easy and fast way to compute a distance field, expressed as an implicit function $\phi(x,t)$, is to employ a Fast Marching technique that provides very fast results at a minimum computational cost.

The evolution of an implicit function under an external velocity field can be written as

$$\phi_t + \vec{v} \cdot \vec{\nabla}\phi = 0 \quad (1)$$

where sub-index indicates a partial derivative with respect to that variable. If we assume that the velocity field at the flow front is normal to the implicit function ϕ itself, $v = V_n n$ with V_n constant. We can rewrite (1) as

$$\phi_t + V_n \cdot |\nabla\phi| = 0 \quad (2)$$

See [4] for details on the discretization and integration of this equation. We can define some geometric concepts that will be used in RI modeling by computing the distance function $\phi(x,y)$ in the whole domain. Figure 2 (left) depicts an example of the distance function computed over a 2D rectangular domain. In this case, the zero-level set of the function is assumed to be located at symmetric the center of the part. It can be easily observed that the just computed level set function possesses maximum value at the four corners of the part.

Figure 2. Distance function $\phi(x,y)$ computed outwards in an isotropic radial infusion of a rectangular mold (left) and with isotropic permeability variation (right).

Since permeability variations in the reinforcements would alter the velocity field during the process, the equation (2) can be computed with the imposed V_n value depending on the changes in the permeability values of non-homogeneous isotropic reinforcements throughout the piece. Figure 2 (right) shows the Distance field pattern computation with the same geometry but considering that the permeability value is double on the right half part and in correspondence the V_n value is also double.

2.1 Distance field computation with anisotropic materials

Non-isotropic reinforcements would alter the flow front shape and hence the flow pattern accordingly to the permeability of the textile. The in-plane permeability values of a fabric can be defined with different procedures. In [6] the results of a benchmark towards standardization of permeability measurements can be outlined. Darcy's law can model the resin flow through a porous

medium:

$$\vec{V} = -\frac{\bar{K}}{\mu \phi} \nabla P \quad ; \quad \bar{K} = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & k_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where \vec{V} is the volume averaged Darcy velocity, ϕ is the porosity, μ is the viscosity, P is the pressure and \bar{K} is the textile permeability tensor. This tensor can be diagonalized to define the three principal permeability values of textile reinforcement. It is usually assumed that the first two principal permeability k_1 and k_2 lie in the plane of the fibre and the third one k_3 is oriented through the thickness. In our work, the effect of the non-isotropic fabric was tested in [5] and hence its influence on the elliptic flow pattern was characterized using artificial vision techniques as shown in Figure 3.

The in-plane flow pattern is thus elliptic and oriented at an angle θ_E rotated between the warp direction and the principal flow direction as shown in Figure 4. The computed parameters a, b define the main axis of the ellipse defined by the flow pattern in a given instant during filling.

Figure 3. Flow pattern characterization in non-isotropic textiles with Artificial Vision Package

Figure 4. 2D flow characterization experiment with no-isotropic textile

Once the no-isotropic permeability effect on the flow pattern is characterized, the distance field function $\phi(x,t)$ can be computed redefining the level set equation (1) as follows

$$\phi_t + \vec{v} \cdot (\bar{M} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where \bar{M} represents the material effect on the flow pattern, and it is defined as a tensor and in 2D states a rescaling and rotation of the elliptical deformed space. Since the permeability values are defined as $k_1=a^2$ and $k_2=b^2$, the value of \bar{M} can be computed as follows

$$\bar{M} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_E & -\sin \theta_E \\ \sin \theta_E & \cos \theta_E \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The computation of equation (4) with the flow pattern characterization defined above, gives the Distance pattern computation according with the deformed space as can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Distance function $\phi(x,y)$ computed outwards in a no-isotropic radial infusion of a rectangular mold experimented as depicted in Figure 4.

2.2 Application in Process Design. Edge Pattern function Λ

An appropriate fast determination of the pre-arrangement of the Resin infusion injection line consist in computing numerically the Laplacian of the distance field $\Lambda = \phi_{xx} + \phi_{yy}$, as described in [1]. This function $\Lambda(x,y)$ distinguishes geometrically the distance flow encounters because second derivatives identify large curvatures. This function $\Lambda(x,y)$ corresponds to the medial axis in the case of having an homogeneous permeability domain and states the set of points that are equidistant to at least

two points of the boundary of a part.

In this work an application of the procedure is given using a carbon-fiber car body for the prototype IDEA CEU CAR [7] with high performance, very light weight developed for a Fuel efficiency competition, see Figure 6.

Figure 6. Idea CEU Car.

In order to show the capabilities of the proposed technique, we present in this section the results of computing the Distance pattern and Edge pattern as Performance Geometric Indicators in the pre-design of RI gate arrangement of a car body composite part. Since the method is not limited to 2D geometries, it has been extended to a more complex 2D shell part. The application example described below shows the capability of the procedure with the definition of the pre-design of a channel network layout by means of the Distance field computation and the Edge Pattern function.

Figure 7. Distance Pattern (left) and Edge Pattern (right) with window areas as thin laminates with isotropic permeability variation. Perimetral vent

Figure 8. Distance Pattern (left) and Edge Pattern (right) with window areas as holes treated as vent lines and perimetral vent.

Figure 9. Distance Pattern (left) and Edge Pattern (right) with no window areas but rib as vent lines and perimetral vent.

Figure 10. Distance Pattern (left) and Edge Pattern (right) with window areas as thin laminates with isotropic permeability variation and rib as vent lines and perimetral vent.

Figure 11. Mold and filling strategy for car body upper part with no windows as stated in previous computations. Strategy corresponding to Figure 10

3 LEVEL SET AS COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK IN LCM PROCESSING

The main awareness is that the methodology treated in previous sections is based on the geometry of the flow path through the mold. Another interesting application is focused on obtaining a real time computational tool that allows one to characterize the dynamic flow behavior of the flow front during filling.

3.1 Flow front shape and velocity measurement during filling

In next figures are shown the results of an experiment carried out in a rectangular rigid mold with a constant pressure injection line on the left. Two areas of textiles with different isotropic permeabilities are placed in order to yield flow distortions during filling. The objective was to obtain the value of V_n from equation (2). Then the flow is assumed to be normal and scaled outwards from previous image, see Figure 12.

Figure 12. Level set ϕ function for consecutive flow fronts

The values of V_n are then calculated from equation (2) using an upwind technique with the level set functions obtained directly from the images.

$$V_{n,i} = \frac{\phi_i - \phi_{i-1}}{\Delta t |\nabla\phi|} \quad (6)$$

Normal velocity values are computed for each mold location (in gray colors, see Figure 13) on each time instant during filling and give us information in real time of the velocity field variations during filling due to the textile permeability variations.

Figure 13. Computation of local velocity V_n during filling in real time. Flow front dynamical behavior characterization during filling due to textile permeability variations

3.2 Flow encounters monitoring during filling

Another real time application of the level set computation as geometric indicator consist in processing numerically the Laplacian of the distance field $\Lambda = \phi_{xx} + \phi_{yy}$, as flow encounters marker. This function $\Lambda(x,y)$ is computed very fast during filling as outlined in Figure 14, Figure 15 and Figure 16

and can be used to forecast the evolution of the resin flow in a fast non-physical simplified manner.

Figure 14. Mold filling image obtained with Artificial Vision (AV) (left), computed flow front (middle) and Level set ϕ as a signed distance function (Right)

Figure 15. AV Flow front shape definition (a), Outwards fast marching computation (b), Distance Pattern function (c) and Edge pattern function (d)

Figure 16. Flow encounters location indicator during filling. Last filled area estimation

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work have been presented a numerical procedure that allows one to predict process

performance indicators that can be used on the pre-design of a LCM process with a desired resin flow pattern. Since the flow fronts filling time can be related to the distance of the flow path, in this work, we propose a numerical technique that computes numerically approximate distance fields by invoking computational geometry concepts that can be used for real time applications due to that alternative LCM physical simulation is computationally expensive. Moreover, we have presented a computational and technological framework based on level sets that allows one to monitor the flow motion under dynamic behavior during filling and establish geometric reference benchmarks for robust processing.

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